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GEORGE EMIL PALADE
UNIVERSITY OF MEDICINE,
PHARMACY, SCIENCE, AND
TECHNOLOGY OF TARGU MURES

International Conference

Resilient Multicultural Societies in the Face of Hybrid Threats

16-17.01.2025, Targu Mures, Romania

Aula Magna, N. Iorga Street no. 1
Hybrid Format

PROGRAM

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10.00-11.00- Official opening, (Romanian, hybrid form)

Keynote addresses

Assoc. prof. Mihaela Daciana Natea, PhD, ESDMS Director, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures (UMFST G.E.Palade Tg. Mures), Romania

Prof. univ. Hedi Saidi, PhD HDR, Universities Sousse (Tunisia) si Catholique de Lille (Franta), Chevalier de la Legion d'honneur, Chevalier des Palmes Academiques, Agrégé d'histoire

Full Professor Luis Tomé, Director of the Department of International Relations at the Autónoma University of Lisbon: “ Hybrid threats and the intersection with multicultural dynamics”

Coffee Break

11.30-13.30 – Panel 1 – Radicalisation, populisme, et sociétés multiculturelles – French and English session

Moderators:

Prof. univ. Hedi Saidi, PhD HDR, Universities Sousse (Tunisia) and Catholique de Lille (Franta), istoric, Chevalier de la Legion d'honneur, Chevalier des Palmes Academiques, Agrégé d'histoire

Assoc. prof. Mihaela Daciana Natea, PhD, ESDMS Director, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures (UMFST G.E.Palade Tg. Mures G.E.Palade Tg. Mures), Romania

Assoc.prof. Ploșteanu Nicolae, PhD, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures

Rouag Abla, PhD, University of Constantine, Alger - The mechanisms for social réintégration of prisoners in Algeria

Ben Hassine Hafedh Ibrahim, PhD, Université de Sousse, Tunisie - Le traitement de la question du populisme au temps de la révolution numérique : le cas tunisien

Konzali Manel, PhD, Université de Sousse, Tunisie - Les institutions sociales dans la société Tunisienne et la résilience face aux effets de la technologie : défis et opportunités

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Mhenni Mourad, PhD, Université de Sousse, Tunisie - La Tunisie face aux menaces hybrides : quand les mouvements islamistes exploitent les fragilités d'une transition inachevée

Bilel Saoudi, PhD, Institut Supérieure De l'Histoire de la Tunisie Contemporaine - La Jeunesse Tunisienne entre instrumentalisation et radicalisation : Itinéraire des djihadistes

Hedi Saidi, PhD, Université de Sousse, Tunisie, Université Catholique de Lille, France - L'histoire des minorités en France. Un passé impensé

Brocca Luca, Just Access e.V., Heidelberg - Satellite Networks and Disinformation Warfare: The Role of Space Technologies in the Russia-Ukraine Conflict and Implications for EU Security

Prof. univ. Ludmila Rosca, PhD Strengthening the Resilience of Democratic Institutions in the EU Enlargement Process

Prof. Ciekanski Zbigniew, PhD, Prof. Żurawski Sławomir, PhD, Oskierko Marcin, PhD State Academy of Applied Sciences in Chełm, Poland - The Migration Crisis as a Tool of Hybrid Warfare - Case Studies at the Borders of the European Union

Devuyt Youri, PhD, Vrije Universiteit Brussel, Belgium - The European Union's Perception and Handling of Hybrid Threats in the Candidate Countries during the Accession Process

15.30-17.00 – Panel 2 – Disinformation and Resilience in Multicultural Societies – English session – on site

Moderators:

Prof.univ. Goudenhoft Gabriela, PhD, University of Oradea, Romania

Lecturer Lucian Sacalean, PhD, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania

Lecturer Tocila Doru, PhD, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania

Prof univ. Goudenhoft Gabriela, PhD, University of Oradea, Romania - Trust Dynamics in Democratic Governance: Unraveling the Impact of Political Distrust on Institutional Legitimacy and Societal Unity

Assoc. prof. Ploeșteanu Nicolae, PhD, Lecturer Boantă Adrian PhD, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania - Hybrid threats and political parties in the context of the Romanian European Parliament elections

Lecturer Lako Cristian, PhD, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania - Kin-State Relations and Media Flow: The Transylvanian Hungarian Minority in the Mureș County, Romania

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Ceusan Ilie Florin, PhD student, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania - The Role of Civil Society Organizations in Combating Disinformation: Successes, Failures, and Future Directions in Romania in the EU context

Lecturer Tocila Doru, PhD, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania - Special Operations Forces As An Interagency Catalyst In Combating Hybrid Threats: A Brief Study Case Of The Republic Of Moldova

Assist. prof. Anca Rusu, PhD student, AI Tools and Hybrid Threats: The Use of Artificial Intelligence to Manipulate Public Opinion and Deepen Divisions in Multicultural Societies

Assoc. prof. Mihaela Daciana Natea, PhD, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania - Disinformation as an Economic Weapon. Is There a Fine Line Between Information and Inducing Badwill?

Lecturer Buhajoti Ana, PhD, University of Tirana, Albania - The globalization of Artificial Intelligence

Prof. univ. Iulian Chifu, PhD, National Defense University, Romania, Rational choice and errors in decision-making: Ukraine, Gaza, Nagorno-Karabakh

15.30-17.00 – Panel 3 – Kremlin's aggression and crisis management – English session – on - line

Moderators

Assoc. Prof. Ejev Cristina, PhD, Moldova State University,
Assoc.prof. Mocanu Veronica, PhD, Moldova State University, Republic of Moldova
Bîrlădeanu Natalia, PhD student, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania

Assoc. Prof. Ejev Cristina, PhD, Moldova State University, Republic of Moldova - International Cooperation In Combating Cyberterrorism

Lecturer Stejaru Selena, PhD, Moldova State University, Republic of Moldova - Multilateralism Towards The Application Of Artificial Intelligence Based On Human Rights And Democratic Values

Rotari Natalia, PhD student, Moldova State University, Republic of Moldova - Cyber-terrorism – current manifestation of the terrorist threat

Assoc.prof. Mocanu Veronica, PhD, Moldova State University, Republic of Moldova - Enhancing readiness and strategic power to prevent and manage information crises

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Bîrlădeanu Natalia, PhD student, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania - Conflict and negotiation in the history of the elites from the Gorbachev regime to the Putin regime. From the Soviet Union to the formation of new independent states. From the Soviet nomenclature to the oligarchy

Solomon Marcu-Andrei, Free Russia Foundation, Brussels Office, Belgium - Europe's hidden defense: the present and future contributions of the Russian democratic opposition towards combating the Kremlin's hybrid warfare

Mârzac Elena, PhD student, Moldova State University, Republic of Moldova - Strategic Communication in Security and Defense: Essential for Crisis Management and National Cohesion

Garbatovschi Valeria, PhD student, Moldova State University, Republic of Moldova - The European Education Area - a catalyst for the development of resilient society

Beltei Margareta, PhD student, Moldova State University, Republic of Moldova - Multiculturalism, Human Rights And Hybrid-Threats: Building Resilience In Modern Societies

Coffee Break

17-30 -19.30 – Panel 4 - Human dimension of resilience building – on site

Moderators

Assoc. prof. Felix Hodos, PhD, University "December 1, 1918" in Alba Iulia, Romania
Alin Tomus, University "1 Decembrie 1918" in Alba Iulia

Assoc. Prof. Costea Simion, PhD, researcher Costea Maria, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania - The European Commission's Criteria and Support Measures for national parliaments as Functioning Democratic Institutions EU Enlargement countries

Gutu Andrei, PhD student, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania - Effects of hybrid warfare on public opinion in the Republic of Moldova

Barbat Vlad, associate lecturer, "Bogdan Voda" University of Cluj-Napoca, Romania - Is European Rule of Law Effective ? Protection mechanisms against exterior threats. Case Study: Romania, Hungary, Poland

Assist. prof. Andreea-Maria Tacşa, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania - Sport and Foreign Policy during the Communist Regime

Assist. prof.r Ungur Mircea Ciprian, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania - Football, a factor of globalization

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Assoc.prof. Țurcanu Florin, Szabo-Csiffo Barna, Magdaș Laurențiu, Țurcanu Dana Simona, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science and Technology of Târgu Mures, Romania - Study on the Optimization of the Physical Component of the Training Process at the Level of Juniors A by Educating the Motor Quality Resistance

Assoc. prof. Felix Hodos, PhD, University "December 1, 1918" in Alba Iulia, Romania, Mihai Daniel Sandru, The Human Security in the Age of Artificial Intelligence: From Social Networks to Network Society

Assoc. prof. Valentina Cornea, PhD, University "Dunărea de Jos" in Galați, Assoc.prof. Alin Tomus, PhD University "1 Decembrie 1918" in Alba Iulia, In Electoral Competition Without a Political Party. Motivations, Context and Legal Resources for Independent Candidates in the Republic of Moldova

17-30 -19.30 – Panel 5 –The Competition for Hearts and Minds in European Multicultural Societies - on line

Moderators:

Assoc. Prof. Cristina Morari, PhD, Moldova State University, Republic of Moldova
Kleszczewska-Albińska Angelika, Management Academy of Applied Sciences, Warsaw

Assoc. Prof. Cristina Morari, PhD, Moldova State University, Republic of Moldova - EU Role In Strengthening Resilience In The Republic Of Moldova

Assist.prof. Filimon Luiza-Maria, PhD, Ovidius University of Constanta, Romania - Radical Right Surges – Outliers or Norms? A Process Tracing Analysis of the Radical Right in the European Parliament after the 2024 European Elections

Prof. Rosca Mariana, PhD and Prof. Ciobanu Rodica, PhD Moldova State University, Republic of Moldova - Strength in Uncertainty: Evaluating Moldovan Resilience in the 2024 Presidential Elections.

Stretea Andreea, Babeș-Bolyai University of Cluj Napoca, Romania - From Vulnerability to Resilience: Security and energy Policy Transformations in Central and Eastern Europe Amid the Ukraine Conflict

Spînu Stela, Moldova State University, Republic of Moldova - Dynamics of Intercultural Communication in a Neurological Context

Assist.prof. Kleszczewska-Albińska Angelika, PhD, Management Academy of Applied Sciences, Warsaw, Poland - Preventive program for building psychological resilience in people living in countries neighboring international military conflicts

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Gala Dinner 20.00

Second day - 17.01.2025

10.00-11.30- Panel 6 Science Diplomacy and Propaganda in the EU context - on site -

Moderators

Assoc. Prof. Simion Costea, PhD, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania

Lecturer Lucian Sacalean, PhD, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania

Lecturer Lucian Sacalean, PhD, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania - The Young Generation, Between Information Consumption and Misinformation

Veronica Zaharagiu, PhD, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania - From Propaganda Through Poetry to Facebook Disinformation

Lecturer Razvan Paraianu, PhD George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania - Populism and the revolt against the system. Lessons of the past and present day vulnerabilities

Assoc. prof. Mihaela Daciana Natea, PhD, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania - From Academia to Diplomacy: Science and Diplomacy as Intertwined Policies for Building Resilience and Combating Hybrid Threats.

Lecturer Cristian Lako, PhD, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania - Resilient Multicultural Societies in the Face of Hybrid Threats -Meme Wars in Romania

10.00-11.30- Panel 7 Georgia's accession efforts - on line -

Moderators

Dr. Archil Chochia, Researcher, Tallinn Law School, Tallinn University of Technology, Estonia

Assoc. Prof. Costea Simion, PhD, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania

Giorgi Ustiashvili, PhD, Caucasus University, Georgia - Social Right of Company Director Under Georgian Law

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Tatia Uberi, PhD, Caucasus University, Georgia - Challenges and Opportunities of Self-Employment in the Contemporary Labour Market: An Examination of Legal Frameworks

Irine Kherkheulidze, PhD, Caucasus University, Georgia - Rape as socio-cultural phenomena - a key to tackle gender-based violence

Irine Bokhashvili, PhD, Caucasus University, Georgia - The Role of the Constitutional Court of Georgia in Aligning Criminal Procedure Legislation with European Standards

Levan Mosakhlshvili, PhD, Caucasus University, Georgia - Europeanization of Georgian Energy Legislation: Approximating Legal Frameworks with EU Energy Policy

Levan Gotua, PhD, - Expansion of Georgian Financial Sector from Perspective of Association Agreement between EU and Georgia

Coffee Break

12-13.30 Panel 8 - Democratic societies facing hybrid threats - on site

Moderators

Assoc. Prof. Costea Simion, PhD, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania

Veronica Zaharagiu, PhD, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania

Lecturer Lucian Sacalean, PhD, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania
Civil society and resilience. Between the decisions of Brussels and the needs of the communities

Veronica Zaharagiu, PhD, Assoc. prof. Natea Mihaela Daciana, PhD, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania - A Constructivist Perspective over Hybrid War and Disinformation

Assoc. Prof. Costea Simion, PhD, researcher Costea Maria, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania - Strategic Partnerships and Civil Society: The EU-Australia Free Trade Agreement in an Evolving Geopolitical Context

Prof. univ. Radu Carp, PhD – University of Bucharest, Romania - Putinism as a thin ideology or bricolage? Theoretical outcomes related to the radicalization of the support for Russian Federation authoritarian regime

Dragos Burghelia, PhD student, - Resilience of the multicultural communities. Case study local elections in Romania

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12-13.30 – Panel 9 Challenges in legal approximation efforts for Georgia’s EU Accession - on line

Moderators

Dr. Archil Chochia, Researcher, Tallinn Law School, Tallinn University of Technology, Estonia

Assoc. Prof. Costea Simion, PhD, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania

Levan Darbaidze, PhD, Caucasus University, Georgia - Legal and Practical Challenges in Safeguarding the Rights of Juvenile Witnesses

Simoni Takashvili, PhD, Caucasus University, Georgia - Infringement of Special Categories of Personal Data and the Data Subject’s Rights Under GDPR and Georgian Law

Balan Aliona, PhD student, Moldova State University, Republic of Moldova - A historical overview of competition in the context of the European integration of the Republic of Moldova

Lecturer Vasilcovschi Nicoleta, PhD, Universitatea, "Stefan Cel Mare" Suceava, Romania - Economic Diplomacy of Georgia and its strategic role for European Integration

Nino Kharitonashvili, PhD, Caucasus University, Georgia - The role of the Court of Justice in the implementation of EU policy through the method of comparative interpretation

Givi Adamia, PhD, Caucasus University, Georgia - Compatibility of Standardization Agreements with EU Competition Law: Legal Insights

Maka Kartoza, PhD, Caucasus University, Georgia - Consumer information Standard according to EU and Georgian Laws

13.30 -15.00 Lunch

15.00-16.00 - Round table and Book presentation

Coffee break and farewell

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USEFUL INFORMATION FOR THE ONLINE PANELS

UMFST G.E. Palade - RCCI is inviting you to a scheduled Zoom meeting.

Topic: Resilient Multicultural Societies in the Face of Hybrid Threats - Day1

Time: Jan 16, 2025 09:30 Bucharest

Join Zoom Meeting

<https://us06web.zoom.us/j/81006720927?pwd=RNGmOk1B1Nd2nqlr10oazncukPpR6Z.1>

Meeting ID: 810 0672 0927

Passcode: 737643

UMFST G.E. Palade - RCCI is inviting you to a scheduled Zoom meeting.

Topic: Resilient Multicultural Societies in the Face of Hybrid Threats - Day2

Time: Jan 17, 2025 09:30 Bucharest

Join Zoom Meeting

<https://us06web.zoom.us/j/82366342143?pwd=gn52L3c8NQECIaEku9CACRyu1Ol48c.1>

Meeting ID: 823 6634 2143

Passcode: 949079

Scientific committee

Chairs

Hedi Saidi, PhD – Professeur, Université Catholique de Lille, France, Président d'honneur de la revue académique "L'Europe Unie", France, Chevalier de la Légion d'Honneur

Mihaela Daciana Natea, PhD – Associate Professor, ESDMS Director, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures (UMFST G.E.Palade Tg. Mures), Romania

Scientific coordinators

Assoc. prof. Gabriela Goudenhoft, PhD, University of Oradea, Romania

Assoc. prof. Felix Hodoș, PhD, University "December 1, 1918" in Alba Iulia, Romania

Assoc. prof. Cristina Morari, PhD, State University of Moldova, Republic of Moldova

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Members

Maria Costea, PhD – Researcher, Gheorghe Sincai Institute of Social Sciences and Humanities of the Romanian Academy

Simion Costea - PhD – Associate Professor, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures (UMFST G.E.Palade Tg. Mures), Romania

Abla Rouag, PhD - Directrice du LAPSI, Professeur université de Constantine 2, Algérie

Anne-Françoise Déquière - Professeur des universités, Université de Lille III, France

Emmanuel Jovelin, PhD - Professeur des Universités. Titulaire de la chaire de travail social CNAM, France

Maya Belouan, PhD - Directrice du Département de sociologie- Institut catholique de Lille, France

Mohamed Jerbi, PhD - Professeur des université, FLSH-Université de Sfax, Tunisie

Bilel Saoudi, PhD -Enseignant /chercheur à l'Institut national de l'histoire contemporaine de la Tunisie

Hassine Hafed, PhD – Professeur, FLSH-Université de Sousse- Tunisie

Claudio Bolzman, PhD - Professeur, l'Université de Genève, Suisse

Hamoudi Rouag, PhD - Professeur à l'Université de Constantine 2, Algérie

Sofiène Moussa, PhD - Enseignant/chercheur FLSH -Université de Sousse, Tunisie

Jean Foucart, PhD - Professeur des universités, Belgique

The organizing committee

Chair

Assoc. prof. Mihaela Daciana Natea, PhD, ESDMS Director, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures (UMFST G.E.Palade Tg. Mures), Romania

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Co-Chair

Prof. Hedi Saidi, PhD, Catholic University of Lille, France, Sfax University, Tunisia, Constantine University Algeria, Knight of the Academic Palms

Lecturer Lucian Săcălean, PhD, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures (UMFST G.E.Palade Tg. Mures), Romania

Veronica Zaharagiu, PhD, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures (UMFST G.E.Palade Tg. Mures), Romania

Assoc. Prof. Simion Costea, PhD George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science and Technology of Targu Mures, Romania

Members

Maria Costea, PhD, “Gheorghe Șincai” Institute of Social and Humanities of the Romanian Academy in Targu-Mures, Romania

Lecturer Lako Cristian, PhD, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures (UMFST G.E.Palade Tg. Mures), Romania

Cristian Măgură, PhD student, Paul Valery University Montpellier 3, France

Assoc. prof. Nicolae Ploeșteanu, PhD, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures (UMFST G.E.Palade Tg. Mures), Romania

Doru Constantin Tocilă, PhD, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures (UMFST G.E.Palade Tg. Mures), Romania

Aliona Bălan, PhD student, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures (UMFST G.E.Palade Tg. Mures), Romania

Natalia Bârlădeanu, PhD student, George Emil Palade University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Science, and Technology of Targu Mures (UMFST G.E.Palade Tg. Mures), Romania

Laura - Simona Todoruț, PhD student, Ovidius University Constanța, Romania

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